

Report of the 2nd transnational workshop (TNWS 2)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101000471.

22nd February 2022
Zoom/hybrid conference
11h30 – 16h30 CET

TNWS2

OBJECTIVES

Four main objectives were identified for the second transnational workshop (TNWS 2):

1. Briefly present the Sm@RT project and its progress
2. Exchange on innovative technologies/digital tools can help answer your needs
3. Get an opportunity to see what the other partners' countries propose in terms of technology use for sheep and goats
4. Meet some of the participants 'for real'

ORGANISATION AND ATTENDEES

Due to Covid-19 ongoing restrictions, the original organisation which was a face-to-face meeting in France was replaced by a hybrid Zoom conference. Indeed, some of the partners' countries were able to join the meeting from a room, where some of their participants were sitting. That was the case for the UK, France, Israel, and Estonia. The Italian, Norwegian, Irish, and Hungarian participants joined individually the Zoom meeting. The main meeting was hosted by the UK partner. The TNWS 2 took place on the 22nd of February 2022 at 10:30 am CET for 4 hours with 1 hour lunchbreak. The meeting was a multi-lingual plenary session and a series of breakout sessions by country. In total, there were 8 breakout rooms and 4 sessions (one on feeding/grazing, one on health/welfare/reproduction, one on milking/fattening and one on flock management). The agenda of the meeting is detailed in annex 1.

A total of 60 people participated in this second TNWS, 11 from France, 6 from the UK, 5 from Ireland, 4 from Hungary, 8 from Norway, 6 from Estonia, 4 from Israel and 16 from Italy. More than a third of participants were farmers.

The French group – hybrid

The UK group – face to face and hosting the Zoom meeting

The slides used during the meeting are presented in annex 2.

SOLUTIONS RETAINED BY THE WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS

During the plenary session, the project was presented to the participants, as well as the preliminary global results on the farmers' needs in terms of technology and digital innovations, based on the NWS results and global survey. Then participants were shown the number of solutions identified by all countries (68 in total: 11 from the UK, 3 from Israel, 6 from Norway, 4 from Estonia, 11 from Italy, 4 from Hungary, 19 from France and 10 from Ireland).

The main cross-activity was for participants to look at the solutions proposed from the other countries, and to vote on the ones they preferred (solutions market approach). Four sessions were organised, to cover the main topics (feeding/grazing, health/welfare/reproduction, milking/fattening, and flock management). Some of the solutions proposed were presented in more than one session. Some solutions were also presented by more than one country. Participants were asked not to vote for their own country solutions. In each breakout session, participants had the list of solutions proposed for the topic in an excel file, with the links to PPT slides, or to videos, so they could visualise the solutions.

After visualisation, they discussed in their country group which solution they preferred. The whole participants came back in the plenary session to give their votes.

The preferred solutions by topic are shown below (the 'heart' symbol shows the votes).

1. Feeding/Grazing:

Feeding/Grazing			
SmartFence/Virtual fence 			
Pregnancy scanning 			
Milkmeter 			
Postdried hay technology 			

2. Health/welfare/reproduction:

Health/Welfare/Reproduction			
EID hand-held wand/data loggers 			
Pregnancy scanning 			
Happy Factor algorithm 			
Water meter 			
Ultra High Frequency 			
GPS & proximity ear-tags 			

3. Milking/fattening:

Milking/Transformation			
Milk tank weighing 			

Fattening			
<p>EID hand-held wand/data loggers</p>			
<p>EID tags</p>			
<p>EID-enabled weighing trough</p>			

4. Flock/herd monitoring

Flock/Herd monitoring			
<p>EID hand-held wand</p>			
<p>Aptimiz</p>			
<p>Milk meter</p>			
<p>Data recording system</p>			

ANNEXES

Annex 1 - agenda

Agenda:

What	UK/Ireland	France/Italy Norway/Hungary	Estonia/Israel
Project presentation & game	10.30-11.00	11.30 – 12.00	12.30- 13.00
Breakout session on Feeding/Grazing	11.00 – 11.20	12.00 – 12.20	13.00 – 13.20
Vote	11.30 – 11.40	12.30 – 12.40	13.30 – 13.40
LUNCH (~1 HOUR)	11.40 – 12.45	12.40 – 13.45	13.40 – 14.45
Breakout session on health/welfare/reproduction	12.45 – 13.15	13.45 – 14.15	14.45 – 15.15
Vote	13.15 – 13.25	14.15 – 14.25	15.15 – 15.25
Breakout session on milking/fattening	13.25 – 13.40	14.25 – 14.40	15.25 – 15.40
Vote	13.40 -13.50	14.40-14.50	15.40 – 15.50
Breakout session on flokc management	13.50 – 14.05	14.50 – 15.05	15.50 -16.05
Vote	14.05 – 14.15	15.05 – 15.15	16.05 – 16.15
Conclusions & feedback	14.15 – 14.30	15.15 – 15.30	16.15 – 16.30

Annex 2 - slides

Sm@RT - Small Ruminant Technology

2nd Transnational Workshop – 22nd February 2022

Carte réalisée avec Cartes & Données - © Artisque

Welcome! Tere tulemast!
Bienvenue!
Benvenuti!
Üdvözöljük!
Velkommen! שלום

Good practices

- Mute yourself unless you want to say anything
- Stop your video if you are not a facilitator
- Quit 'Full Screen' mode to be able to see the 'chats'

Good practices

- During the plenary session, use 'Chat' to ask questions

- During the breakout rooms, use the chat in the room or use your microphone (unmute yourself).
- Update your username to make it more explicit (country_name_surname) to facilitate the breakout rooms allocation.
- Put letters in front of your name to precise your country:

FR - France
IL - Israel
HU - Hungary
IR - Ireland

IT - Italy
NO - Norway
EST - Estonia
UK - UK

Examples :
UK_Ann McLaren
NO_Lise Grova

Welcome!

Goals for today:

- Present briefly the Sm@RT project
- Exchange on innovative technologies/digital tools can help answer your needs
- Get an opportunity to see what the other partners' countries propose in terms of technology use for sheep and goats
- Meet some of you 'for real'

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LUNCH (~1 HOUR)	11.40 – 12.45	12.40 – 13.45	13.40 – 14.45
Breakout session on health/welfare/reproduction	12.45 – 13.15	13.45 – 14.15	14.45 – 15.15
Vote	13.15 – 13.25	14.15 – 14.25	15.15 – 15.25
Breakout session on milking/tattening	13.25 – 13.40	14.25 – 14.40	15.25 – 15.40
Vote	13.40-13.50	14.40-14.50	15.40 – 15.50
Breakout session on flokc management	13.50 – 14.05	14.50 – 15.05	15.50-16.05
Vote	14.05 – 14.15	15.05 – 15.15	16.05 – 16.15
Conclusions & feedback	14.15 – 14.30	15.15 – 15.30	16.15 – 16.30

Sm@RT - Small Ruminant Technology

Sm@RT presentation

Sm@RT: Sm@RT: Small Ruminant Technology – PLF and Digital technologies for small ruminants

3 years
Starting Jan 2021

Objectives :

- To create a European **network** around the **use of PLF and digital technologies** in small ruminants
- To encourage **knowledge exchange**, new technologies **adoption** and **communication** between farmers and stakeholders of the small ruminant sectors.

Partners & Countries:

UK	SRUC	Moredun
Ireland	Teagasc	
Norway	NIBIO	
France	INRAE	In Extenso
Italy	Agris	
Hungary	EMBL	
Estonia	EMBL Maastricht	
Israel		

Important dates to remember

National workshops
Every 6 months

International workshops
Every 6 months after the national workshops

PLF/Digital technologies demonstration/training
On the Digifarms and 'Innovative Farms' in 2022 / 2023

-
- Step 1**
 - 1a: Identification of farmers needs
 - 1b: Inventory of corresponding PLF/digital technologies
 - Step 2**
 - Selection of PLF/digital technologies suitable to the different contexts and countries
 - Step 3**
 - Farmers barriers and testimonies
 - Step 4**
 - Assessment of farmers acceptance of the different technologies from the sessions, visits, and farm demo on Innovative Farms and Digifarms.
 - Step 5**
 - Definition of a European dissemination and uptake strategy for PLF and digital technologies in small ruminants systems

What have we done?

Online survey (May – July 2021) (669 answers)

List of farmers' needs for tools to help them at:

1. Feeding/Grazing
2. Health/Welfare
3. Reproduction
4. Flock/Herd management
5. Fattening/Milking

Workshops (Sept – Oct 2021)

A little game....

1

	Ireland?
	United Kingdom?
	Hungary?
	Italy?
	Estonia?
	Israel?
	Norway?
	France?

Zoom poll / hand raised in rooms

A little game....

2

	Ireland?
	United Kingdom?
	Hungary?
	Italy?
	Estonia?
	Israel?
	Norway?
	France?

A little game....

3

Ireland?
United Kingdom?
Hungary?
Italy?
Estonia?
Israel?
Norway?
France?

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Sm@RT – breakout sessions

1 room	1 online breakout room (IRE)	1 online breakout room (HU)	1 online breakout room (IT)	1 room	1 room + some people online (IL)	1 online breakout room (NO)	1 online breakout room (FR)

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Breakout Session 1

Feeding/Grazing

Feeding/Grazing

SmartFence/Virtual fence 	EID weighcrate + autosorter 	Grazing management app 	Automated grass measurement
Pregnancy scanning 	Ration/Feeding Software 	Drone 	Portable NIR
Milkmeter 	Automatic feeder 	Connected Fence 	GPS collars
Postdried hay technology 	HappyGrass 	Drone with thermal camera 	GPS collars with behaviour

Breakout Session 1
Feeding/Grazing

2 best ones?? ❤️❤️

plenary

LUNCH!

Back in 1 hour

Breakout Session 2

Health/Welfare/Reproduction

Health/Welfare/Reproduction

EID hand-held wand/data loggers	Data recording system/ Flock recording app	EID weigh crate and autosorter	FEC software (FecPak G2)
Pregnancy scanning	Parentage test	Worming /vaccinating gun	Sheep conveyor
Happy Factor algorithm	Camera	Somatic Cell counter	Weather/ environmental station
Water meter	Automatic feeder	Alpha detector	3D imaging
Ultra High Frequency	Walk Over Weigh	Environmental enrichment	EID-enabled water trough
GPS & proximity ear-tags	Guard dog & high tensile fence	Milk feeders for kids/lambs	GPS collars & behaviour information

Breakout Session 1

Health/Welfare/Reproduction

2 best ones?? ❤️❤️

plenary

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Breakout Session 3

Milking/Fattening

Fattening

<p>EID hand-held wand/data loggers</p>			
<p>EID tags</p>			
<p>EID-enabled weighing trough</p>			

Milking/Transformation

<p>Milk tank weighing</p>			

Horizon 2020
Programme

Breakout Session 3

Milking/Fattening

2 best ones?? ❤️❤️

Breakout Session 4

Flock/Herd management

Flock/Herd monitoring			
EID hand-held wand 🇮🇹 🇩🇪	Worming/Vaccinating guns 🇮🇹 🇩🇪	EID weigh crate and autosorter 🇮🇹 🇬🇧 🇮🇹	Milking parlour with EID 🇫🇷
Aptimiz 🇫🇷	Environmental station + cooler 🇮🇹	Automatic feeder 🇫🇷	Camera 🇫🇷
Milk meter 🇮🇹	EID-enabled water trough 🇮🇹	Data recording system 🇳🇴	

Breakout Session 4

Flock/Herd management

2 best ones?? ❤️❤️

plenary

Next steps:

3rd National Workshop: early June 2022

3rd Transnational workshop: early July 2022

Feedback on today:

Did you enjoy the meeting and discussions?

How was the meeting organisation?

Zoom poll/ on paper

Horizon 2020
Programme

Merci beaucoup! A bientôt!

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Thank you very much! Good bye!

Tusen takk! Ha det bra! Nagyon szépen köszönjük! Viszontlátásra!

Grazie mille! Arrivederci

תודה רבה לך! שלום!

Täname väga! Head aega!

- @H2020Smart
- H2020-smart
- h2020smart
- H2020-Sm@RT

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